

Structured Reflective Feedback From Students Reveals Areas Of Academic Self-Improvement In Teaching And Learning For The Field Of Management

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 11, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 15, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Reflections, Higher education, Oral Presentations, Principles Of Teaching</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5510715</p>	<p><i>Feedback has the capability of helping to identify areas of academic self-improvement when used wisely. The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate how an academic has used structured reflective feedback from students to reveal areas of self-improvement in terms of teaching and learning practice. A case study is used for this research. A key result indicates that the module provided a valuable learning experience to many students. This was especially highlighted by the benefits derived from the required student oral presentations and by working in groups. These aspects helped many students to build their confidence in terms of interacting with other people. On the other hand, some students found the oral presentations to be challenging due to the heavy workload as they did not have enough time to prepare well for them. Most of the students stated that the academic should continue lecturing the module because she lectures in a positive manner that could enable them to be more positive for the exam. It is recommended that more academics should resolve to seek feedback from students in terms of their teaching and learning practices as it may reveal areas of self-improvement for them.</i></p>

Introduction

“Feedback or knowledge of results is a requirement for effective goal setting”. These words by Ciancia, Klein and Seijts (2010) suggest that feedback is important when setting effective goals, such as improving ones teaching practice. Williams and Brennan (2004) further indicate that higher educational institutions are re-evaluating the importance of student feedback that needs to be collected effectively and used wisely. Student feedback that is widely used may assist in improving an academic’s teaching practice, to the benefit of future students and the institution. Using such feedback to identify areas of academic self-improvement is one way in which it can be used wisely. Locke and Lathan (2002) states that feedback is a cornerstone of goal setting and other motivational interventions. Research has shown that failure to attain a goal or performance standard has a negative influence on an individual’s affective state (Ilies, De Pater, & Judge, 2007). Subsequently, if one attains a goal of improving one’s own teaching practice, then logically one’s state of mind or disposition would be enhanced. Improvement-oriented feedback may be associated with increased satisfaction or positive attitudes which may lead to better performance (Sedikides & Hepper, 2009). This shows that feedback can yield positive results for an academic whose goal is to improve his or her performance.

Yeo and Neil (2004) allege that individuals who are performance goal orientated, tend to view mistakes and negative feedback as an evaluative threat to self. While individuals with the learning goal orientation seeks out challenges and persist in striving for goal attainment despite obstacles and setbacks (Cianci, Klein, & Seijts, 2010). This suggests that academics who want to improve their teaching practice needs to be learning goal orientated, and not solely performance goal orientated. They need to seek to learn for themselves and not always pursue performance in terms of academic pass rates or success. An academic should seek to enrich him or herself with the goal of enriching the lives of others. Using student’s reflections as feedback is one method that may be used to achieve this goal.

Feedback-seeking behaviour is a valuable resource for individuals in work and educational settings and it enhances learning and performance (Crommelinck & Anseel, 2013). Iqbal, Ramzan and Arain (2016) points out that teachers may seek feedback in a verbal or written manner from their students on a particular aspect of their teaching. Individuals who seek feedback through written reflections directly seek the views and opinions of others, including their supervisors, co-workers or even students. This shows that feedback seeking interventions could be beneficial for an organisation and for an academic.

Therefore, the purpose of this paper is to demonstrate how an academic has used structured reflective feedback from students to reveal areas of self-improvement in terms of teaching and learning practice. The use of reflections in education; the importance of feedback and improvement strategies in teaching and learning are

firstly discussed. The context of the study is then provided followed by the research methodology, results and discussion.

The use of reflection in education

Barnard (Barnard, 2011) brings to our attention that the concepts of “reflection” is mostly used by education scholars and is sociologically a feature of ‘the production of self’ in contemporary society. Reflections are typically used when teachers consciously think and trace the uncertainties of their professional practices (Iqbal, Ramzan, & Arain, 2016). In view of this, it seems that in education, scholars or teachers should make conscious effort to search out new ways to grow professionally. Reflective practice gives teachers an opportunity to participate in a perpetual growing process that requires an on-going critical reflection over their classroom practice (Larrivee, 2000). This means that ongoing reflective practice by an academic can assist him or her to improve their classroom teaching.

Schön (1983) was one of the first to mention the term “reflective practice”, pointing out that reflection is a thoughtful contemplation of one’s own experience in applying knowledge to practice. Reflection includes the process of conscious thinking to trace any gaps of one’s professional practice (Iqbal, Ramzan, & Arain, 2016). Therefore, in order for an academic to identify areas of self-improvement one would have think about his or her own teaching practices. Reflective practice pays critical attention towards teachers’ professional values and finding out theories that works behind their day-to-day actions (Bolton, 2010). By making use of student reflective feedback in education it can provide an academic with opportunity to acknowledge, reflect and interpret different students’ experiences with the goal of self-improvement.

Burniskes and Meibubbaum, (2012) points out that reflective students’ feedback is important, however, its reliability and validity is difficult to measure. The role of reflection in the feedback process is mostly uncontested and the emphasis is on the view that various feedback studies that ascribe to reflection may differ (Goh & Walker, 2018). In view of this reflective feedback practice can be important for an academic and used without being contested by various scholars in their studies. However, Sham, Cheng, and Fitzgerald (2017) state that there exists an unsystematic use of feedback by academics to improve teaching practices.

Different studies have been done on students doing reflections for different purposes. Swart (2017) reports on a study that was conducted in electrical engineering module. The purpose was to highlight how an academic in the have effectively used an institutional learning management system, called Blackboards, to promote student engagement and academic success through online reflective self-assessments. Moreover, another study in Post Graduate Diploma qualification at the University of the Witwatersrand used reflections to enable lecturers to develop reflexive approach to evaluate their teaching and learning assumptions (Dison, 2016).

In summary, student reflections allow teachers to consciously think about their professional practices and requires them to make efforts to search for ways to grow. They also provide an opportunity for one to acknowledge and reflect on student’s feedback. However, there are some concerns relating to reflections that include measuring its validity and reliability. Furthermore, literature suggests that some academics do not systematically use feedback in higher education to improve their teaching practice. Nevertheless, its importance is well documents in the literature, as the following section shows.

The importance of feedback in education

Yanagizawa (2008) points out that individuals who are frequently seeking feedback demonstrate higher goal attainment and learning compared with individuals who do not do so. Kelman (2017) concede that instrumental people seek feedback because it has informational value that helps them to meet their goals and regulate their behaviour. Feedback is important because through it individuals can discover opportunities for skills improvement, higher performance and promotion (Crommelinck & Anseel, 2013). This shows that in order for individuals to find out how they are performing, and at the same time being goal driven, it is necessary for one to seek feedback frequently. Above all feedback seeking individuals can develop creative relevant skills and gain fresh perspectives on their ideas. Feedback from students may assist an academic to improve his or her performance by being creative and introducing new teaching and learning methods. De Stobbeleir, Ashford, and Buyens (2011) acknowledges that employees who sought feedback from various sources showed greater creativity at work.

According to de Luque, Wollan, and Boyi (2019), the frequency of employee feedback decreases as they stay longer in an organisation. A decline in feedback frequency may decrease employee’s organisational commitment, resulting in an increased turnover (Vandenberghe, et al., 2019). This shows that employees may have different intentions and purposes for seeking feedback and in the long term they lack continuity. Frequent feedback seeking is therefore very important and should not be a once off process, especially for academics in higher education. Continuity would assist an academic to keep on reflecting on students’ feedback with the goal

of self-improvement. This may lead to an academic continually investigating his or her own teaching practices with the goal of self-growth, self-improvement, and improved student learning.

Evidence shows that in medical education feedback is considered as an integral and important element of teaching that encourages and enhances the learner's knowledge, skills, and professional performance (Shrivasta, Shrivasta, & Ramasamy, 2014). Altmiller (2016), stresses that delivery of feedback should be constructive in nature and support growth and confidence while maintaining the dignity of the other. Feedback plays an important role for both learners and teachers' growth, and it can improve their performance.

To summarise, feedback seeking behaviour in education is usually done by individuals who are goal driven, as it assists them in identifying areas of self-improvement. Furthermore, it can help individuals be more creative in their work. Academics should not fall into the trap of ignoring feedback but should consistently seek it with the aim of improving teaching and learning practices. In order for feedback to be effective, an academic need to obtain constructive feedback that can be practically applied to change his or her teaching practices.

Principles in teaching and learning

Chew et al., (2018) posits that there must be a fundamental change in the paradigm of teaching and learning. The authors propose principles of change that are built on the science of learning. These principles are as follows:

- Teaching and learning are complex; these processes defy easy, universal solutions.
- Teachers have a huge impact, for better or for worse, on what students learn and how likely they are to remember and use that knowledge appropriately.
- Learning is the primary responsibility of the student, facilitated by the faculty.
- We should measure the evidence of teaching effectiveness directly through student learning and indirectly through changes in student attitudes and increases in student retention.
- Teachers, especially teachers of psychology, should be encouraged to examine their own teaching using empirically based methods, viewing their classrooms as laboratories for applied psychology.
- Ongoing effective assessment is essential to teaching and learning; both teachers and students need opportunities to use feedback to improve.
- Effective assessment practices involve matching assessment formats to intended measurement goals. Measuring what students know (content knowledge) and what they can do (skills) are both essential and require different assessment methods.
- Student evaluations can provide a perspective on effective teacher qualities but should not be used as the only measure of teaching effectiveness.
- Effective teachers understand how the courses they teach fit into the overall curriculum and work collaboratively with departmental colleagues to ensure students achieve desired learning outcomes.
- All undergraduate psychology majors deserve attention, guidance, support, and career-specific resources, not just the graduate school bound.
- The undergraduate curriculum should ensure that those who go into the workforce have relevant and adequate preparation to do so.
- Technology can enhance learning experiences but must be judiciously incorporated and skilfully delivered in course architecture to produce increments in learning.
- Teachers must have a better understanding of individual and cultural differences to create the most favourable learning climate.

It is very possible that the performance of an academic, in terms of teaching practice, will improve when making use of a number of these strategies and principles. Measuring teaching practice through student learning is very applicable to this study, as student reflections of what they have experienced or learned will be used. Student evaluations using reflections will provide an academic with information on what students enjoyed or found challenging in the module. It may also guide the academic to stop or continue with a specific teaching practice. Academics must also seek to create the most favourable learning climate, which means that they need to know their students and their experiences. One way of obtaining these experiences can be through using student reflections. Therefore, in the context of this study, student experiences in a Management Training module were obtained.

The context of the study

The module used in this research is Management of Training I (MOT1) that is a compulsory offering or module that forms part of the Diploma: Human Resources Management qualification, comprising of approximately 18 modules in total (Central University of Technology, 2019). Students must obtain a minimum of 384 credits to successfully complete this three-year qualification. This qualification offers different career opportunities such as being a human resources manager, industrial relations specialist and training specialist.

MOT1 is split over two semesters and offered in the second year of the Diploma. The purpose of the module is to address the need for sound education training and development practices and to assist learners in adapting to the new education and training outlook in South Africa. Students write two tests per semester that contributes to their course mark. In order for students to write the final examination, they must obtain a minimum course mark of 40%. Two examination papers per year requires students to distinguish, demonstrate, explain and discuss what they have learned in the module. A final mark is the combination of a 50% course mark and a 50% examination mark. Students must obtain a final mark of more than 50% for both semesters to successfully pass the module.

The focus of MOT1 is on training concepts and terminology. It also offers a broad overview of a training circle; learning theories; adult learning principles and methodology; role and function of human resources development (HRD) within an organisation. Furthermore, it involves training legislation; policies and HRD practices; and development and assessment of learning and evaluation of training and development. MOT1 has a credit value of 24 that indicates that students need to spend at least 240 notional hours dedicated to this module. Table 1 below presents the structure of MOT1 where semesters one and two are shown along with the outcomes and assessments weights.

Table 1. Structure of HRM1

Semester one Time Period	Main outcomes	Assessment
Week 1 – 4	Orientating students regarding the module Managing training and development in organisations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The concept of training, education and development • Why do organisations offer training? • The place and role of the Training and Development function in the organisation’s structure. (T&D) • Understand managerial approach to training. • Training and development policy • The role of the training professional 	
Week 5 – 8	The education, training, and development environment in South Africa <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Human Resources Development (HRD) Strategy for South Africa (2010-2030) • National Skills Development Strategy III (NSDS III) • Training related legislations 	Week 6 = Test 1 Weighting: 50%
Week 9 – 12	Administration of training and development in the organisation. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training costs and budgets • Training and development facilities 	Week 12 = Test 2 Weighting: 50%
Week 13 – 16	Learning theories and principles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theories of learning and factors affecting learning. • Adult learning 	Week 14 = Course mark finalisation
	Main assessment	First semester examination
Week 1 – 5	Determining training and development needs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The concept of training needs assessment or analysis (TNA). • Techniques of needs assessment • Job analysis for training purposes • Identifying student needs and data gathering 	Week 4 = Test 1 Weighting = 50%
Week 6 – 10	Programme design and development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elements of curriculum design in outcomes-based education and training. • Purpose statement • Formulating learning outcomes • Sequencing content and training programme planning • Competency-based training 	Week 8 = Test 2 Weighting = 50%
Week 10 – 12	Preparing and presenting training and development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparing training 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presenting training 	
Week 12 – 14	Assessing learning and evaluating training and development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student assessment • Programme evaluation: Concepts and design 	Week 14 = Course mark finalisation
	Main assessment	Second semester examination

Method

Quantitative and qualitative data was obtained to better understand student experiences in the MOT1 module. This data was underpinned by a series of close-ended and open-ended questions that originated from published literature relating to student experiences in a mentorship programme (Swart, Coughlan, & Joannou, Student perspectives of a peer mentorship programme introduced at a university of technology in South Africa., 2019). The data was obtained from a structured reflective questionnaire that students filled at the end of the second semester of 2019.

Fathi&Behzadpour, (2011) state that in education various reflective practices are proposed such as, writing reflective diaries, reflective learning journals, reflective stories and reflection through students' feedback. The researcher encouraged her students to fill in the reflective questionnaire about their classroom experiences in the MOT1 module in a written structured way.

A research population comprises the potential contributors of interest to a study (Luck & Kappenman, 2011). In this study it comprises all the students in two MOT1 classes that the researcher taught during 2019, equalling 92 students.

Only 56 of these students were present in class at the end of the semester who freely volunteered to complete these reflections. This forms the sample size of the study that relates to convenience sampling. Etikan, Musa and Alkassim (2016) reports that convenience sampling is a type of nonrandom sampling whereby members of certain target population meet practical criteria, such accessibility, availability at a given time and willingness to participate in the study.

A method used for identifying, analysing and interpreting patterned meanings or themes in qualitative data is called thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2013). This was used in this study as the researcher collected and analysed reflections in order to construct meaning from them for self-improvement.

According to Walton (2016), ethics is described as research that involves human subjects or participants that may raise: a distinctive and complex ethical, legal, social and political issue. It is mainly concerned in the analysis of ethical issues that are raised when people are involved as participants in research. This study is supported by the Faculty Research and Innovation Committee of Management Science at the Central University of Technology, Free State. Ethical clearance from the institutional planning unit was obtained beforehand. The researcher maintained a respectful attitude towards the participants and highlighted that their participation is completely voluntary and that their responses are confidential. No academic consequences would result from their participation.

Results and Discussion

The biographic profile of the students registered for MOT1 included gender, age and home language. The dominant home language was Sesotho, indicative of the Free State Province in South Africa (Mahloane & Trausan-Matu, 2015) while the dominant age group was between 20-25 years (see Figure 2 and 3). This age group validates them as undergraduate students who are in their second year who have less than two years out of secondary or high school career. In South Africa, the average age to complete a schooling career is 18 years (Kruger & Sonono, 2016) Most of the students that participated in this study were females (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Student's gender

Figure 2. Student's language

Figure 3. Students age group

The questionnaire required students to report on their experiences in the module. Closed questions, featuring Likert scale, were used on previous research which focused on student experiences in a mentorship programme (Swart, Coughlan, & Joannou, Student perspectives of a peer mentorship programme introduced at a university of technology in South Africa., 2019). Sections of the study focused on whether the module was a valuable learning experience; another one was evaluating if students learned new knowledge that can help them to design a quality training programme (see Figure 4). Other sections focused on whether students felt that the module was enjoyable and very challenging to complete.

Figure 4. Students experiences in the module.

The results indicate that out of 56 respondents 44 students agree (17 + 27) that the module was a valuable experience. 48 students (15 + 33) agreed that they learned new knowledge that can help them to design a quality training programme. 40 students (14 + 26) further agreed that they enjoyed the module. The last question provides a mix of results, where 20 students felt that it was challenging, while 17 disagreed with the question. These results may suggest that a heavy workload was experienced by some of the students, as mentioned in the qualitative results of this study that are presented next. However, these results do tend to suggest that this module was a valuable learning experience for students where they learned new knowledge.

Table 2 through 4 presents a breakdown of various themes that emerged from students' reflections. Table 3 focuses on what students enjoyed or found challenging. Table 4 focuses on what the academic in MOT1 should continue or stop doing regarding her teaching practice. Each table is divided in to three columns which include direct quotes from students' reflections, themes with a number in brackets that represents the number of students who mentioned it and relevant supporting literature for the particular theme.

Table 1. Valuable learning experience

Student's reflections	Theme	Literature
<i>"The most valuable experience that I acquired was presentation, reason being it was my first time presenting in front of audience".</i>	How to do a presentation (9)	• Chew et al., (2018)
<i>"I have gained confidence of standing in front of people and presenting as an aspiring HR Practitioner"</i>	Gaining confidence (4)	
<i>"Having to engage in group work and applying certain skills when learning. Learning about presentations and how to conduct a presentation".</i>	Working in group (6)	

Table 2. Enjoyable or challenging.

Student's reflections	Themes	Literature
<i>"I enjoyed the presentations the most because teamwork is better than working alone. The auditorium she introduced us to made us to feel like we are already in a business world"</i>	Doing presentations (11)	• Chew et al., (2018)
<i>"I enjoyed the way the lecturer tackled the module, she made it easy for us to understand it and be able to read without gramming".</i>	Lecturer facilitation (12)	• Sedikides and Hepper, (2009)
<i>"I enjoyed working in groups with another student. The challenging part was presentations".</i>	Working in groups (3)	• Crommelinck and Anseel, (2013).
<i>"The module has a lot of work, and it is challenging".</i>	Workload challenging (5)	

<i>"I did not enjoy the presentation part; it was super challenging, but it helped me with confidence and how to interact with people".</i>	Doing presentations was challenging (5)
<i>"Being given reflective writing exercise while preparing for a test was challenging".</i>	Doing reflection exercise was challenging (3)
<i>"I enjoyed working in groups. Challenge was not being given enough time to prepare".</i>	Time allocation (4)

Table 4. Continue or stop doing.

Student's reflections	Theme	Literature
<i>"Continue, because she conveys lecturing in a positive manner, she clearly indicates that she is familiar with the context and understand it in a wider degree".</i>	Lecturing module (16)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chew et al., (2018) • Iqbal, Ramzan and Arain,(2016)
<i>"I would encourage the lecturer to continue asking series of questions so we can build up our knowledge on the subject".</i>	Asking questions (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Altmiller, (2016)
<i>"When lecturing she clearly make one understand the content and go further explaining by using examples".</i>	Making the module Understandable (3)	
<i>I would suggest that that she continues to make good engagements with students and keep on giving students class activities so that they can be prepared for tests and examination.</i>	Engaging students (3)	
<i>She should continue lecturing the module because she treats students equally.</i>	Treating student equally (2)	
<i>"Continue with student's presentations because it gives us good experience needed for the future."</i>	Presentations (7)	
<i>"She should continue motivating as it makes us to do our best."</i>	Motivating (2)	
<i>"To stop giving us to much work at the short period of time".</i>	Stop giving a lot of work with short period to prepare work (5)	

The students felt that doing presentations in groups was the most valuable learning experience in the module as they gained confidence (as noted in Table 2). Also, they enjoyed doing presentations because they worked in a team. Moreover, they enjoyed how the lecturer facilitated the module because she made it easy for them to understand it in preparation for the main exam. On the other hand, some students found the oral presentations challenging due to the heavy workload, as they felt that there was a lot of work to complete in a short period of time (as noted in Table 3 and 4).

Interestingly, regardless of the challenges faced by some students in terms of the heavy workload, many of them stated that the lecturer should continue lecturing it (noted in Table 4). This may suggest that students feel that the lecturer has no control over the course content but created a favourable learning environment for it. She manifested a positive attitude and indicated by her PPT presentations that she was very familiar with the content. Furthermore, the lecturer should continue to use oral presentations as a means of assessment, as it provides students with good experience which will be needed in the future. However, some students felt that the lecturer should stop giving too much work within a short period of time, as they may struggle with large volumes of work, that may cause them stress or anxiety.

Conclusion

The purpose of this paper was to demonstrate how an academic has used structured reflective feedback from students to reveal areas of self-improvement in terms of teaching and learning practice. Structured reflective

feedback regarding students' experiences and what an academic should stop and continue doing in the MOT1 module were classified into themes. The results indicate that most students had a valuable learning experience in the module and enjoyed it. This was related to the required oral presentations and working in groups (see Table 2). Students also enjoyed how the lecturer facilitated the module (see Table 3). On the other hand, some students found the oral presentations to be challenging due to the heavy workload as they did not have enough time to prepare well for them. Nevertheless, the oral presentations helped many students to build their confidence in terms of interacting with other people. Most of the students stated that the academic should continue lecturing the module because she lectures in a positive manner that could enable them to be more positive for the exam (see Table 4).

The academic reflected on these results and resolved to make the following adjustments to her teaching practice. (1) More time would be given to students to prepare for oral presentations. (2) An additional oral student presentation to be included in the module. (3) Modifying a few classroom PowerPoint presentations to include more group work.

The present study is limited to a singular module in management. However, it does provide insight into how an academic has used structured reflective feedback from students to reveal areas of self-improvement in terms of teaching and learning practice.

Recommendations

It is recommended that more academics should resolve to seek feedback from students in terms of their teaching and learning practices as it may reveal areas of self-improvement for them. This is related to the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning where the main aim is to enhance student learning through improved teaching practices, as the academic in this study has done. This may also lead to benefits for the university by improving student retention rates as they are more likely to achieve academic success.

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